

Organ-of-Corti Cytoarchitecture and the Cochlear Amplifier

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Abstract. Mammalian cochlear amplification is subserved by electromotile outer hair cells (OHCs) cradled within the organ of Corti by a complex, interlocking cellular scaffold whose functional significance cries out for explanation. The prevailing interpretation of the cytoarchitecture traces its origins to the work of Charles Steele and colleagues (Mechanics of Hearing Workshop, Paterswolde, 1993) and has since been considerably elaborated. In this view, the Y-shaped skeleton transmits OHC forces along the organ of Corti, conspiring with phase shifts introduced by traveling-wave delay to create a form of negative damping that amplifies BM traveling waves as they propagate. Here, we develop a general framework for describing the active forces and apply it to show that the prevailing interpretation appears inconsistent with the measured properties of reflection-source OAEs. Indeed, OAE measurements imply that the transverse forces relevant to cochlear amplification occur not at the level of the BM but at the top of the organ of Corti, near the reticular lamina, and are facilitated by longitudinal motion of the Deiters cells. Our results are consistent with a recent model in which cochlear amplification occurs via area deformations of the organ of Corti rather than by direct forcing of the basilar membrane. We reinterpret the cellular scaffolding as a mechanical funnel that collects and distributes OHC forces over a larger area of the organ of Corti.

INTRODUCTION

In the oblique, Y-shaped geometry of the organ of Corti (Fig. 1), one finds the apically tilted electromotile outer hair cells (OHCs) and the basally oriented phalangeal processes (PhP) of the Deiters cells (DC), all sandwiched between the basilar membrane (BM) and the reticular lamina (RL). By analogy with the framing in a truss bridge [1], perhaps this striking, interlocking arrangement evolved merely to provide structural stability to the organ of Corti. Or, as Voldrich and Kolston have suggested [2, 3], perhaps the tilted geometry somehow acts to enhance the response of the basilar membrane. It would certainly be satisfying if something so beautiful were no mere “so what” [4] but also subserved some interesting and important purpose. But if the Y-shaped geometry really does enhance the motion of the organ of Corti, how does it do it? Here, we discuss and evaluate ideas about how the Y-shaped cytoarchitecture contributes to cochlear amplification.

FIGURE 1. Idealized schematic of the Y-shaped geometry of the organ of Corti formed by the longitudinal tilt of the outer hair cells (OHC) and the phalangeal processes (PhP) of the Dieters cells (DC), all sandwiched between the reticular lamina (RL) and basilar membrane (BM). For simplicity, the Y is approximated as an inverted isosceles triangle.

GENERAL ANSATZ FOR THE ACTIVE FORCES

Everything is easier if we simplify the geometry. In the schematic of Fig. 1, the interlocking meshwork has been made regular and symmetric, with the Y approximated as an isosceles triangle. We focus on the structures connected to the Deiters cell located at position x . The hair bundles of the upstream and downstream OHCs are located at positions $x - \Delta$ and $x + \Delta$, respectively. The active forces at location x consist of a “feed-forward” component due to OHC₁ and a “feed-backward” component communicated via the phalangeal process from OHC₂. (Forward and backward are defined with respect to the direction of the forward-traveling wave). Thus, in a very general way, we represent the active force at location x as the sum of these two components:

$$F_{\text{active}}(x) = \gamma_{\text{forward}}D(x - \Delta) + \gamma_{\text{backward}}D(x + \Delta). \quad (1)$$

The feed-forward component is proportional to the response, D , at location $x - \Delta$ and the function $\gamma_{\text{forward}}(x)$ characterizes the strength of this force. (One might think of D as the displacement of the stereocilia, for example.) Likewise, $\gamma_{\text{backward}}(x)$ describes the strength of the feed-backward force, which is proportional to the response at location $x + \Delta$. Typically, the distance Δ spans no more than the width of a hair cell or two—much less than the wavelength of the traveling wave—so the responses at $x - \Delta$ and $x + \Delta$ are generally quite similar in amplitude but differ slightly in their phase due to the traveling wave.

Because Δ is relatively small [5], the responses are well approximated using a Taylor series, so that $D(x \pm \Delta) \approx D(x) \pm \Delta dD/dx$. Using these approximations yields the expression

$$F_{\text{active}}(x) \approx \underbrace{(\gamma_{\text{forward}} + \gamma_{\text{backward}})D(x)}_{\text{local}} - \underbrace{(\gamma_{\text{forward}} - \gamma_{\text{backward}})\Delta \frac{dD}{dx}}_{\text{non-local}}. \quad (2)$$

The active force thus consists of a component proportional to the local response and a component proportional to its spatial gradient. We call the first component the “local” force and the second the “non-local” force. Because we have yet to specify the values of $\gamma_{\text{forward}}(x)$ and $\gamma_{\text{backward}}(x)$, this formulation is quite general.

THE PUSH-PULL MODEL

One way to specify the functions $\gamma_{\text{forward}}(x)$ and $\gamma_{\text{backward}}(x)$ is to attempt to identify the forces relevant to cochlear amplification. Charles Steele pursued this approach back in 1993, developing a model—essentially, a special case of Eq. 2—that has since been considerably elaborated [6]. Indeed, the resulting “push-pull” model has become the prevailing view of how organ-of-Corti cytoarchitecture contributes to cochlear amplification. To understand the idea underlying the push-pull model, we consider the schematic and, following Steele, think about the active forces presumed to drive the transverse motion of the BM via the Deiters cells. First, consider what happens when the OHCs contract. When OHC₁ contracts it pulls up on the DC. At the same time, but with slightly different phase, OHC₂ contracts, pulling down on the RL. This downward force pushes on the DC via the PhP. So the transverse feed-forward and feed-backward forces on the DC are in opposite directions. One-half cycle later, the OHCs expand, and all the forces reverse. Again, the transverse feed-forward and feed-backward forces on the DC are in opposite directions. Thus, if one assumes that the OHCs and PhPs have similar stiffnesses, then γ_{forward} and γ_{backward} have roughly equal amplitude but opposite signs: $\gamma_{\text{forward}} \approx -\gamma_{\text{backward}}$.

When inserted into the general expression for the active force [Eq. 2], this relationship implies that the local force component goes to zero. All that remains is the non-local (or push-pull) component, which simplifies to

$$F_{\text{active}}(x) \approx \underbrace{-2\gamma_{\text{forward}}\Delta \frac{dD}{dx}}_{\text{push-pull}}. \quad (3)$$

In the push-pull model, the active forces depend on the spatial gradient of the response (dD/dx), and therefore (presumably) on the direction of wave propagation [6, 7]. In other words, because forward- and backward-traveling waves have different phase gradients, they may be amplified differently. Unfortunately, this striking prediction has proved difficult to test, principally because any directional dependence to the cochlear amplifier is hard to detect using conventional mechanical measurements, such as laser-Doppler or OCT-based vibrometry. We have recently shown, however, that the push-pull model can be tested using otoacoustic emissions, whose generation involves both forward- and backward-traveling waves [8].

FIGURE 2. Simulated SFOAE levels vs frequency computed in a family of response-matched models of the mouse cochlea (see reference [8] for details). The setting of the force-mixing control knob, μ , varies as a parameter. Each curve represents the loess trend line computed by pooling the responses of 25 in-silico ears obtained by varying the random spatial pattern of micromechanical irregularities. The numbers to the right of the plot give the percent RMS spatial irregularity needed to produce simulated SFOAE levels comparable to those in the local model ($\mu = 0$). (Adapted from reference [8].)

CONSTRAINTS ARISING FROM REFLECTION-SOURCE OAES

Although the obvious strategy—comparing OAE data with model predictions obtained using different micromechanical implementations of the cochlear amplifier (i.e., local vs push-pull forces)—fails if naively applied, we have developed a “magic force-mixing control knob” that facilitates well-controlled numerical experiments. The knob controls a parameter we call μ , which varies continuously from 0 to 1. Turning the knob does several things: First, it modifies the nature of the active forces [see Eq. 2], from the entirely local ($\mu = 0$) to the completely push-pull ($\mu = 1$); intermediate settings produce a mix of forces to which both terms in Eq. 2 contribute. Thus, the value of μ specifies the fraction of the total active force that is push-pull in character. Second, and despite changing the underlying active forces, the knob leaves both the shape of the forward-traveling wave and the micromechanical irregularities responsible for wave scattering invariant.

Both the details of knob implementation and an account of its application to cochlear mechanics can be enjoyed elsewhere [8]. In a nutshell, we verified that push-pull forces render cochlear wave propagation non-reciprocal and anisotropic: when forward-traveling waves are amplified, reverse traveling-waves are squelched (and vice versa). Here, we use the knob to ask “What is the actual, biological value of μ ?” To answer this question, we compare our model results with the known, measured properties of stimulus-frequency OAEs to derive constraints on the relative strengths of local vs push-pull forces.

Constraints from SFOAE Level

First, we consider OAE level (Fig. 2). Comparing mean simulated SFOAE levels with data from mouse, we see that the local model gives fairly realistic levels [9] but that increasing μ quickly drives OAEs below the measurement noise floor, which is generally around -20 dB SPL. Thus, this comparison suggests that the biological value of μ is no larger than about 0.2 or 0.3. But care is required—this conclusion incorrectly assumes that round-trip gain is the only factor influencing OAE level. OAE level also depends on the size and nature of the mechanical irregularities. In these simulations we have taken the irregularity to be in the active forces and to have an effective RMS magnitude of about 0.5%. Larger irregularities would give larger emissions. Thus, we can compensate for the reduced round-trip gain by increasing the size of the irregularities. The values shown to the right of the plot give the percent irregularity needed to yield OAE levels similar to those in the local model. Our analysis here is corroborated by the finding that irregularities in active force of at least 80% are necessary to produce realistic OAE levels in a finite-element (FEM) model of the mouse cochlea that incorporates the Y-shaped geometry [10].

Thus, to constrain the biological value of μ , one first needs to answer the question: How large are the irregularities in the actual cochlea? Unfortunately, we do not really know. There are so many potential sources of irregularity that identifying the dominant one and determining its effective size is difficult. At the end of the day, all we really have is a hand-waving intuitive sense that irregularities larger than, say, 5% are probably unrealistically large. But your intuition may differ. So although the constraints arising from OAE level appear suggestive, they are not especially strong.

FIGURE 3. Simulated SFOAE delay ratios (SFOAE delay / near-CF BM delay) vs frequency computed in a family of response-matched models of the mouse cochlea. The setting of the force-mixing control knob, μ , varies as a parameter. Each curve represents the loess trend line computed by pooling the responses of 25 in-silico ears obtained by varying the random spatial pattern of micromechanical irregularities. The data points give empirical delay ratios computed from data in the literature. Key to symbols: \blacklozenge mouse [12]; \bullet guinea pig [13]; \blacktriangle chinchilla [11]; \blacksquare guinea pig [14]; \star gerbil [15]; \blacktriangledown cat [14]; \circ mouse finite-element (FE) model [10, 16]. (Adapted from reference [8].)

Constraints from SFOAE Delay

The constraints arising from OAE delay are more definitive (Fig. 3). To deduce these constraints, it helps to normalize the SFOAE delay by the group delay of the BM transfer function at its peak [11]. The resulting delay ratio has been measured experimentally and appears roughly constant, both across species and across frequency, at least in the basal region of the cochlea. Comparing the measured values, which are generally somewhere between 1.5 and 2, with results obtained by turning the knob suggests that μ values in the cochlea are less than about 0.2. By contrast, our analysis predicts that the delay ratios in push-pull models are considerably smaller, even less than 1. This prediction is again consistent with delay ratios computed using the mouse FEM model [10].

We these insights, we can return to our question about how the knob is set in the real cochlea. Evidently, comparisons with both OAE level and delay indicate that the biological value of μ is less than about 0.2. Indeed, the data are consistent with a value as small as $\mu = 0$. In other words, the OAE data imply that *the active forces are primarily local in character*.

CYTOARCHITECTURAL INTERPRETATION OF LOCAL ACTIVE FORCES

Recall that in the prevailing view, push-pull forces dominate (Eq. 3), because γ_{forward} and γ_{backward} in Eq. 2 are assumed to have opposite signs. But in the real cochlea, the reverse appears to be true: the local component is large and the push-pull component is small. According to Eq. 2, this suggests that γ_{forward} and γ_{backward} must be nearly equal (not equal and opposite, as implied by the push-pull model). How can one interpret the relation $\gamma_{\text{forward}} \approx \gamma_{\text{backward}}$ physically using our schematic of the Y-shaped cytoarchitecture?

In the prevailing view, γ_{forward} and γ_{backward} are taken to have opposite signs because the forces relevant to cochlear amplification are assumed to act on the BM via the Deiters cells [17, 18]. At this location near the DC, the two arms of the Y produce forces that point in opposite directions. But our analysis has shown that γ_{forward} and γ_{backward} must have the same sign. In other words, the two arms of the Y must produce forces that act in the same direction. As illustrated in Fig. 4, this happens at two locations within the organ of Corti. Most importantly, it happens at the top of the organ of Corti near the RL. At this location the transverse components point in the same direction. Interestingly, it also happens near the DC, but in the longitudinal direction.

To see this, note that when OHC_1 contracts (see Fig. 4A), it pulls down on the RL. The contraction also pulls the DC longitudinally, towards the left. This causes the PhP to pull down at its apical attachment, augmenting the contraction due to OHC_2 . Thus, both the feed-forward and feed-backward arms of the Y produce downward forces on the RL and leftward forces on the DC. At each location, they act with the same sign. And, one-half cycle later, when OHC_1 expands (see Fig. 4B), it both pushes up on the RL and pushes the DC longitudinally, now towards the right. As a result, the PhP also pushes up at its apical attachment, augmenting the force due to OHC_2 . Again, both arms of the Y act with the same sign at both locations.

Thus, our analysis implies that the transverse forces relevant to cochlear amplification act not at the bottom on the organ of Corti (i.e., the BM), as commonly assumed, but at the “top”. To summarize the argument, our analysis

FIGURE 4. Schematic snapshots of the OHC electromotile forces acting within the longitudinally tilted, Y-shaped geometry of the organ of Corti. The snapshot in panel A occurs during OHC contraction; that in panel B occurs one-half stimulus cycle later, during OHC expansion. The gray dashed lines show the resting positions of the RL, PhPs, and OHCs. (Here, the BM is represented as immobile.) The large black arrowheads show the directions of the OHC and PhP forces, the small dashed red arrows show the directions of the net forces acting on the DC and RL. Because of the Y-shaped truss, the net transverse (i.e., vertical) force on the BM via the DC is small while the net transverse force on the RL is large. The net force on the Deiters cup at the basal pole of the OHC is primarily longitudinal.

shows that to generate realistic SFOAEs, the active forces must be local. This requires that the feed-forward and feed-backward strengths (γ_{forward} and γ_{backward}) be roughly equal, producing forces that act in the same directions. This in turn indicates that the transverse forces relevant to cochlear amplification act at the top of the organ of Corti, facilitated by longitudinal motions at the DCs.

This conclusion is consistent with recent mechanical measurements, which show that the RL generally moves more than the BM and that the DCs have a significant longitudinal component to their motion [19, 20]. Thus, our analysis provides independent support for the “overtuned” model [21], in which cochlear amplification occurs via OHC-induced area deformations at the top of the organ of Corti (see also [22, 23]).

For ease of analysis and exposition, the model discussed here is, of course, highly simplified. For example, the geometry of the Y has been approximated as symmetrical, so that the feed-forward and feed-backward distances are the same. With only minor modifications, however, our major conclusions appear robust to these approximations. For example, the almost entirely longitudinal net force predicted at the DC is a consequence of the assumed symmetry. In a more realistic geometry, the forces and motions are presumably somewhat oblique [24].

It remains curious that OAE generation in the finite-element (FEM) model of the mouse cochlea discussed above [10] requires such sizeable irregularities (Fig. 2) and yields SFOAE delay ratios substantially less than one (Fig. 3). By intent, the FEM model makes no explicit assumptions about the forces relevant to cochlear amplification, supposing instead that these forces will emerge spontaneously, unbiased by theoretical hypotheses or preconceptions, from ostensibly realistic assumptions about the functional anatomy and material properties. And yet, unlike the cochlea it presumes to represent, the model behaves almost exactly as if the push-pull mechanism were somehow baked in to the model DNA. Although the mechanisms operating in FEM models are not always easy to identify, perhaps the difficulty here relates to another unresolved issue with the model. In particular, the FEM model is known to significantly overestimate the group delay of BM frequency responses [10]. Interpreted in the spatial domain, this behavior implies that the model wavelength is much too short. As a result, the FEM analogue of the response gradient (dD/dx) appearing in Eq. 2 is presumably unrealistically large. As a result, the model may artificially inflate the relative contribution of push-pull forces, rendering wave amplification non-reciprocal.

In their roundabout way, otoacoustic emissions have led us to a new conception of the role of the Y-shaped cytoarchitecture in cochlear mechanics. The Y is not a pushmi-pullyu but more of a funnel, anchored to the basilar membrane, that collects and distributes OHC forces over a broad region of the reticular lamina. In other words, the Y is a spatial integrator, summing forces over space, rather than a differentiator. By integrating over multiple hair cells, the Y reduces the amplifier’s sensitivity to internal noise.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the reviewers for their helpful comments (see below) and Mary Ann Cheatham at Northwestern University and James Dewey at the University of Southern California for generously sharing their data. Supported by grants R01 DC003687 (CAS) and R21 DC019712 (AA) from the NIDCD/NIH.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

François Deloche: Thank you for this nice paper. Your analysis of OAE amplitudes and delays to make inferences about the directionality of amplification forces, and thus on the possible role for the Y-shaped cytoarchitecture, is very insightful. The analysis involves many mathematical-modeling techniques that are not presented here but can be found in the Appendix of your recent paper. You focus instead on the interpretation of the results, which makes it an accessible work. I have a few questions:

- You write that the push-pull model has been the prevailing view of cochlear amplification. Is that really so?

Reply: We refer here not to cochlear amplification *per se*, but to the functional role of the Y-shape in distributing

the forces relevant to amplification.

- I could not follow your explanation at the end on how the RL and DC junction move. Why does the DC junction move longitudinally but not the RL? And the opposite for transverse motion: Why does it affect the RL but not the DC junction? If I watch the supplementary video provided by Cooper et al. [19] to explain their interpretation of their data, the RL moves longitudinally as much (or more) than the DC junction. But in the text you only mention longitudinal motion for the DC junction. Is that based on some other data?

Reply: In the diagram, we implicitly assume that the BM moves little and that RL moves less longitudinally than the DC. At the location of the OHC₂ hair bundle, for example, the contraction of OHC₁, transmitted via the PhP, pulls the RL to the left, whereas the simultaneous contraction of OHC₂ pulls it to the right (Fig. 4, panel A). Similarly, at the DC, the transverse forces from the OHC and the adjoining PhP are in opposite directions. Both the Olson and Puria labs have shown that the RL moves quite differently (i.e., less “crazily”) than the “hotspot” region near the DC [25], a finding that differs from the earliest reports.

- While reading the abstract, my initial idea was that the Y shape integrates forces from several OHC rows to push/pull on the BM, as the Y shape indeed resembles the shape of a funnel. But your explanation seems the opposite: That the integration is for the forces pushing/pulling the RL transversely. However, I am wondering whether my first intuition could also be valid? For instance, if the RL can push on the TM, then it may be possible to see the funnel up-to-down rather than down-to-up. In fact, I present at MoH a work suggesting that the TM viscous resistance could be important.

Reply: Our interpretation emerges quite naturally from our simplified framework, and fits well with our previous work that reached similar conclusions by analyzing other types of data. Of course, other interpretations are possible, and we look forward to hearing more.

- On the spatial integration of forces, do you believe it could have implications for the generation of OAEs? Specifically, if it serves to smooth the local mechanical impedance, it could reduce the effective size of the irregularities inside the cochlea. A second, more difficult question would then be: How does this mechanism compare in strength to longitudinal coupling from TM viscoelastic properties?

Reply: These are good questions. Unfortunately, we do not really know the dominant micromechanical source of the irregularity, although it is natural to suspect hair cell-to-hair-cell variations in active force. It is therefore hard to quantify how much the spatial integration of forces would smooth or reduce them. We suspect, however, that the smoothing effect will not be large for reflection-source OAEs. The spatial integrator we propose would smooth over distances corresponding to a couple longitudinal rows of OHCs; that is, over distances much less than a wavelength. Coherent reflection theory implies that the irregularities that contribute most to the net reverse-traveling wave (i.e., to the OAE) have spatial periods that are considerably larger (i.e., on the order of one-half a wavelength). On the issue of differences between longitudinal coupling through the PhP vs. the TM, the Freeman group has found that the decay constants of TM waves are also on the order of a wavelength; that is, roughly an order of magnitude larger than the longitudinal distance spanned by the PhP. So, again, the two processes operate on different spatial scales and are thus not easily compared.

Renata Sisto: I read with great interest your wonderful paper. Although I agree with you that the fact that the RL moves much more than the BM and the compliance of the DCs makes the hypothesis that a large contribution to the traveling wave in the peak region comes from the upper part of the organ of Corti very plausible, your argument here, and in your *PNAS* paper [8], leaves me with some perplexities:

- Citing the work by Steele, you define an active force on the BM that contains both a local and a non-local feed-forward/feed-backward term. But this is not Steele’s model: in his model, the active force is due only to the non-local “push-pull” term [18].

Reply: In general, feed-forward and feed-backward forces give rise to both local and non-local force terms, and our analysis includes both (along with a “magic knob” that can vary their relative strength). The push-pull model you refer to is a special case in which the local force term is set to zero. As we discuss in the paper, the push-pull model disregards the local force term because the model assumes that the forces relevant to cochlear amplification act on the BM (via the DCs).

- Can you clarify something about the model you use to illustrate your analysis? In the *PNAS* paper, you call the coefficient of the local active force γ_{local} . Is γ_{local} real-valued? If so, I have a hard time seeing how the model

can amplify traveling waves.

Reply: Indeed, for purposes of illustration we adopt a locally active model in which γ_{local} is pure imaginary. The model is a close variant, adapted to mouse, of several recent models derived to describe coherent wave amplification in the mammalian cochlea [21, 26, 27, 28].

Julien Meaud: Thank you for your talk. Just some quick comments:

- On your conclusion slide, I do not think it is right to say that amplification in push-pull models is “anisotropic”; it should be “directional”.

Reply: Yes, technically you are right; it is the cochlear gain medium, not the resulting amplification, which is anisotropic in such models. In engineering and materials science, anisotropy refers rather narrowly to the directional dependence of a local physical property. Here, we are (mis)using the term in the spirit of its broader physics meaning (“different in different directions”, as illustrated, for example, by the “temperature anisotropy of the cosmic microwave background,” although in our case there are only two directions that are relevant). We simply mean that the push-pull mechanism renders the active properties of the cochlear gain medium different in the two directions. As a result, the model amplifies waves traveling in one direction while squelching those traveling in the other.

- More fundamentally, how can we reconcile this simple, phenomenological model with more anatomically realistic models (e.g., the mouse FEM model, in which, for example, the PhPs and DCs are represented by stiffnesses)?

Reply: That’s a great question. Needless to say, we have no answer, other than to reiterate the obvious: that both approaches are necessary; that both have their own strengths, weaknesses, and inherent biases; and that it is our collective task to assiduously work both ends of the problem towards a mutual, comprehensive understanding.

Ernst Dalhoff: Your sketches of the various forces and displacements suggest that the DCs cannot induce significant movements of the BM, either transverse or bending. Is anything known about this?

Reply: First, our sketches are just that: highly simplified illustrations that should not be taken to imply that the OHCs *cannot* move (or bend) the BM via the DCs, only that they are relatively poor at doing so. There is now considerable theoretical and experimental evidence for this. For example, George Samaras noted yesterday that for the OHCs to drive BM motion directly, the DCs need to be far stiffer than they appear to be [29]. Furthermore, OCT measurements show that the relative phase of the transverse motion of the DCs is incompatible with power flow from the DCs to the BM; indeed, the DCs appear to be sucking power *from* the BM [21].

Sunil Puria: In defense of our mouse FEM model [10], one of the reasons that our SFOAE/BM delay ratio is so small (see Fig. 3), is that the BM traveling wave in our model has way too much delay. We’re trying to fix this. As for the Y shape, I still stick to that.

Reply: There appear to be two problems with the FEM model, the first related to emission generation, and manifest in the small value of $\tau_{\text{SFOAE}}/\tau_{\text{BM}}$, and the second to the unrealistically long BM delay. This second problem implies that the wavelength of the traveling wave is much too short. As we discuss in the text, perhaps these two problems are related and so admit of a common remedy.

Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh: I have 36 seconds. So just out of curiosity, because the distance spanned by the Y shape is so much smaller than the wavelength of the traveling wave, do you think it feasible to make a coarse-grained model that does not explicitly include the Y, but achieves the same ends via some sort of longitudinal coupling? Based on your expansion and subsequent findings, it appears there is no need to worry about spatial gradients.

Reply: Yes, that is a good question. There are many forms of longitudinal coupling that act over distances shorter than a wavelength. In a coarse-grained model it seems reasonable to suppose that one can account for them in a more phenomenological way, at least until we have better data.

